

Measuring Heart Rate and Spo2

Abdulsalam Essam Abdulkareem

Ashur University, Technical Engineering College, Medical Instrumentation Techniques Engineering, Iraq

Aosaid Jamal Mohammed

Al-Farahidi University, Medical Technical College, Engineering of Medical Devices Technologies, Iraq

Rusul Ali Abd Oun

Al Hussein University College, Medical Devices Engineering Technology, Iraq

Mohammed Abbas Fadel

Al Hussein University College, Medical Devices Engineering Technology, Iraq

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Abstract:

In this work We offer an Arduino Uno based system to measure heart rate and Spo2 based on wavelength. We aim to design a device that is easy to use for the aged people and pregnant women in critical situations, which no longer requires a long time to measure.

This proposed work was accomplished using an Arduino Uno microcontroller, red infrared LEDs, photo sensors, and photodiodes. In this work, we demonstrate that we can use small

devices as an alternative to large devices to measure the health effects on the human body, and it is even possible to use devices much smaller than this device. The proposed system was designed in a laboratory-scale prototype to experimentally verify the system's efficiency, reliability and low cost.

We note that the proposed system can be easily tested and implemented under real conditions on a large scale in the near future, which will be useful in future applications for monitoring human health with small, and easy-touse devices.

Keywords: *Arduino Uno, easy-touse device, heart rate measurement, human health monitoring.*

Introduction

To solve the problem of disturbing the existing heart rate and oxygen detector, a portable heart rate oximeter is proposed in this project. The device can detect and display the heart rate value and blood oxygen percentage of the human body at any time. The instrument gets rid of the burden of traditional medical devices, which greatly reduces the size of the instrument and is easier to carry. The heart rate oximeter designed in this project is smart and portable. It has a wide range of practical applications.

The First Pulse Oximetry

The early model pulse oximeter was invented in the 1970s by Dr. Takuo Aoyagi, a Japanese engineer and bioengineer. His invention incorporated the principles of spectrophotometry to measure oxygen saturation non-invasively Nihon Kohden subsequently produced the first pulse oximeter, named the Ear Oximeter OLV-5100 as seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Ear Oximeter OLV -5100

Surgeon Susumu Nakajima and his associates first tested the device in patients, reporting it in 1975 (Severinghaus, & Honda, 1987). However, Nihon Kohden suspended the development of pulse oximetry and did not apply for a basic patent of pulse oximetry except in Japan, which facilitated further development and utilization of pulse oximetry later in U.S. In 1977, Minolta commercialized the first finger pulse oximeter OXIMET MET-1471 as seen in Figure 2. In the U.S., the first pulse oximetry was commercialized by Biox in 1980 (Masimo Corporation, 2009).

Figure 2. First Finger Pulse Oximeter OXIMET MET-1471

Prevalence of Pulse Oximetry

By 1987, the standard of care for the administration of a general anesthetic in the U.S. included pulse oximetry. From the operating room, the use of pulse oximetry rapidly spread throughout the hospital, first to recovery rooms, and then to intensive care units. Pulse oximetry

was of particular value in the neonatal unit where the patients do not thrive with inadequate oxygenation, but too much oxygen and fluctuations in oxygen concentration can lead to vision impairment or blindness from Retinopathy of Prematurity (ROP). Furthermore, obtaining an arterial blood gas from a neonatal patient is painful to the patient and a major cause of neonatal anemia (Lin, 2000).

Survey of the Problem

Motion artifact can be a significant limitation to pulse oximetry monitoring, resulting in frequent false alarms and loss of data. This is because during motion and low peripheral perfusion, many pulse oximeters cannot distinguish between pulsating arterial blood and moving venous blood, leading to underestimation of oxygen saturation.

Early studies of pulse oximetry performance during subject motion made clear the vulnerabilities of conventional pulse oximetry technologies to motion artifact. In 1995, Masimo introduced Signal Extraction Technology (SET) that could measure accurately during patient motion and low perfusion by separating the arterial signal from the venous and other signals.

Since then, pulse oximetry manufacturers have developed new algorithms to reduce some false alarms during motion, such as extending averaging times or freezing values on the screen, but they do not claim to measure changing conditions during motion and low perfusion (Jopling, Mannheim, & Bebout, 2002).

So there are still important differences in performance of pulse oximeters during challenging conditions. Also in 1995, Masimo introduced perfusion index, quantifying the amplitude of the peripheral plethysmograph waveform. Perfusion index has been shown to help clinicians predict illness severity and early adverse respiratory outcomes in neonates, predict low superior vena cava flow in very low birth weight infants, provide an early indicator of sympathectomy after epidural anesthesia, and improve detection of critical congenital heart disease in newborns. In 2011, an expert

workgroup recommended newborn screening with pulse oximetry to increase the detection of Critical Congenital Heart Disease (CCHD) (Kemper, et al., 2011).

The CCHD workgroup cited the results of two large, prospective studies of 59,876 subjects that exclusively used signal extraction technology to increase the identification of CCHD with minimal false positives. The CCHD workgroup recommended newborn screening be performed with motion tolerant pulse oximetry that has also been validated in low perfusion conditions.

In 2011, the US Secretary of Health and Human Services added pulse oximetry to the recommended uniform screening panel. Before the evidence for screening using signal extraction technology, less than 1% of newborns in the United States were screened.

Today, The Newborn Foundation has documented near universal screening in the United States and international screening is rapidly expanding. In 2014, a third large study of 122,738 newborns that also exclusively used signal extraction technology showed similar, positive results as the first two large studies.

High Resolution Pulse Oximetry

High Resolution Pulse Oximetry (HRPO) as seen in Figure 3 has been developed for in-home sleep apnea screening and testing in patients for whom it is impractical to perform polysomnography. It stores and records both pulse rate and SpO₂ in 1 second intervals and has been shown in one study to help to detect sleep disordered breathing in surgical patients (Chung, et al., 2012).

Figure 3. High Resolution Pulse Oximetry

Microcontroller

A microcontroller is a small computer on a single integrated circuit. A microcontroller contains one or more CPUs (Central Processing Unit) along with memory and programmable Input/Output peripherals. Programming memory in the form of ferroelectric RAM or OTP ROM (One Time Programmable ROM) is also often included on chip, as well as a small amount of RAM.

What is Arduino?

Arduino is an open-source electronics platform based on easy-to-use hardware and software. Arduino boards are able to read inputs (light on a sensor, a finger on a button, or a Twitter message) and turn it into an output (activating a motor, turning on an LED, publishing something online). You can tell your board what to do by sending a set of instructions to the microcontroller on the board. To do so you use the Arduino programming language (based on Wiring), and the Arduino Software (IDE), based on Processing (Anaesthesia UK, 2004).

Over the years Arduino has been the brain of thousands of projects, from everyday objects to complex scientific instruments. A worldwide community of makers, students, hobbyists, artists, programmers, and professionals, has gathered around this open-source platform, their contributions have added up to an incredible amount of accessible knowledge that can be of great help to novices and experts alike.

Arduino was born at the Ivrea Interaction Design Institute as an easy tool for fast prototyping, aimed at students without a background in electronics and programming.

Why Arduino?

Arduino simple and accessible user experience, it has been used in thousands of different projects and applications. The Arduino software is easy-to-use for beginners, yet flexible enough for advanced users. It runs on different types of operating system such as Mac, Windows, and Linux. Teachers and students use it to build low cost scientific instruments, to prove chemistry

and physics principles, or to get started with programming and robotics (Anaesthesia UK, 2004).

Arduino Specifications

There are a lot of Specifications, such as:

Inexpensive - Arduino boards are relatively inexpensive compared to other microcontroller platforms. The least expensive version of the Arduino module can be assembled by hand, and even the pre-assembled Arduino modules cost less than 50\$

Cross-platform - The Arduino Software IDE (Integrated Development Environment) runs on Windows, Macintosh OSX, and Linux operating systems. Most microcontroller systems are limited to Windows.

Simple, clear programming environment to take advantage of as well. For teachers, it's conveniently based on the Processing programming environment, so students learning to program in that environment will be familiar with how the Arduino IDE works.

Open source and extensible software - The Arduino software is published as open source tools, available for extension by experienced programmers. The language can be expanded through C++ libraries, and people wanting to understand the technical details can make the leap from Arduino to the AVR (Automatic Voltage Regulator) C programming language on which it's based.

Open source and extensible hardware - The plans of the Arduino boards are published under a Creative Commons license, so experienced circuit designers can make their own version of the module, extending it and improving it. Even relatively inexperienced users can build the breadboard version of the module in order to understand how it works and save money.

Types of Arduinos

There are 20 different types of Arduino Boards, some of them are:

Arduino classic Nano, is the oldest member of the Arduino Nano family boards. It is similar to

the Arduino Duemilanove but made for the use of a breadboard and has no dedicated power jack. Successors of the classic Nano are for example the Nano 33 IoT featuring a WiFi module or the Nano 33 BLE Sense featuring Bluetooth Low Energy and several environment sensors as seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Arduino Nano

Arduino Micro, is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega32U4, developed in conjunction with Adafruit. It has 20 digital Input/Output pins (of which 7 can be used as PWM outputs and 12 as analog inputs), a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a micro-USB connection, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It contains everything needed to support the microcontroller; simply connect it to a computer with a micro-USB cable to get started. It has a form factor that enables it to be easily placed on a breadboard. The Micro board is similar to the Arduino Leonardo in that the ATmega32U4 has built-in USB communication, eliminating the need for a secondary processor. This allows the Micro to appear to a connected computer as a mouse and keyboard, in addition to a virtual (CDC) serial / COM port, as seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Micro Arduino Figure 2.2 Arduino Micro

Arduino Mega 2560, is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega2560. It has 54 digital input/output pins (of which 15 can be used as PWM outputs), 16 analog inputs, 4 UARTs (hardware serial ports), a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button, as seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Arduino Mega 2560

Arduino UNO, is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328P. It has 14 digital input/output pins (of which 6 can be used as PWM outputs), 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz ceramic resonator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header and a reset button. It contains everything needed to support the microcontroller; simply connect it to a computer with a USB cable or power it with a AC-to-DC adapter or battery to get started. You can tinker with your UNO without worrying too much about doing something wrong, worst-case scenario you can replace the chip for a few dollars and start over again., as seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Arduino UNO

Methods

Components

The main component of this practical research list as follow as:

The MAX30100: Is an integrated pulse oximetry and heartrate monitor sensor solution. It combines two LEDs, a photodetector, optimized optics, and low-noise analog signal processing to detect pulse oximetry and heart-rate signals. The MAX30100 as seen Figure 3.1 operates from 1.8V and 3.3V power supplies and can be powered down through software with negligible standby current, permitting the power supply to remain connected at all times.

Figure 8. The MAX30100

LCD screen with: size 2(row) * 16(column) with I2C extension. Which is used to display results from Arduino screen as seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9. LCD screen

Mini Breadboard 170P: The SYB-170 Mini Solderless Breadboard is named for its 170 points. It has 17 columns of 10 holes, which are separated into two pairs by a central notch, and labeled 1 to 17, as seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Breadboard

Arduino Uno R3: Is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328P. It has 14 digital input/output pins, a 16 MHz ceramic resonator, a USB connection and a reset button, as seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Arduino Uno R3

Power Supply: the main board feeds power either:

By using USB (Universal serial bus) as seen in Figure 12, Or using 9v battery as seen in Figure 13.

6- Breadboard Jumper Wires: These wires used for connection with different lengths and different colors in order to differentiate between them, as seen in Figure 14.

Figure 12. USB

Figure 13. 9v Battery

Figure 14. Breadboard Jumper Wires

Link the Project

The project may be connecting as seen in Figure 15.

Connect (VCC) of LCD , and (Vin) of Sensor with (5V) of Arduino

Connect (GND) of LCD , and (GND) of Sensor with (GND) of Arduino

Connect serial clock pin (SCL) of LCD , and (SCL) of Sensor with (A5) of Arduino

Connect serial data pin (SDA) of LCD , and (SDA) of Sensor with (A4) of Arduino

Figure 15. Link the Project

Programming Arduino

The following steps are done to program the Arduino:

1. Install the Arduino IDE software on computer.
2. Connect the Arduino board to computer using a USB cable.
3. Select the board type and the correct port from the "Tools" menu in the Arduino IDE.
4. Download libraries
5. Write code in the programming window, by using C++ Code , (Appendix-A-)
6. Connect the Arduino board to computer and select the correct port.
7. Click the "Upload" button to transfer the program to the Arduino board.

Principle of the Work

In the mechanism of a standard pulse oximeter, there is an electronic processor paired with a duo of miniature light-emitting diodes (LEDs). One LED emits red light at a wavelength of 660 nm, while the other emits infrared light at 940 nm. Positioned opposite these LEDs there is a

photodiode, typically placed against a translucent part of the patient's body, such as a fingertip or earlobe as seen in Figure 16.

The absorption characteristics of these wavelengths vary significantly between oxygenated and deoxygenated blood. By alternately activating the LEDs—first one, then the other, then both off—the oximeter allows the photodiode to independently detect red and infrared light. This process, occurring around thirty times per second, enables the device to compensate for ambient light and provide accurate readings of oxygen saturation.

The pulse oximeter calculates the amount of light that passes through (i.e., isn't absorbed) by measuring transmitted light. It then generates separate normalized signals for each wavelength. These signals fluctuate over time due to the pulsing arterial blood volume with each heartbeat.

By subtracting the minimum transmitted light from the transmitted light at each wavelength, the device corrects for the influence of other tissues, producing a continuous signal that reflects pulsatile arterial blood flow.

Figure 16. Principal Work of Pulse Oximeter

Compare Results

After running the project, there is a series of experiments to evaluate its quality, which indicate error rate not exceed 5% , Figure 17.

Project Problems

Our challenge stemmed from the scarcity of reliable tools, leaving us with only subpar options. The inflated prices of sensitive tools compounded the issue, as their poor quality hindered their functionality.

Figure 17. Compare Results

Conclusion

Pulse oximetry is simple, convenient, inexpensive tool which has unique advantage of continuous noninvasive method of measuring Hb saturation and measurement of oxygen

saturation provides conclusions about the function of the lungs.

By determining the saturation of the venous blood, carbon dioxide analysis is a means for assessing metabolism circulation and ventilation.

Pulse oximetry prevent 93% of avoidable anesthesia mishaps. The goal that we wanted to achieve in the project is lower cost with higher accuracy than other devices.

Future Works

To enhance the device in the future, features like recording measurements and connecting it to the internet for remote control and access could be added, along with developing a smartphone app for easy measurement tracking. These additions could increase the device's effectiveness and make it more user-friendly and efficient.

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